

FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION WITH SERVICE QUALITY AT 5-STAR HOTELS IN HO CHI MINH CITY

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Abstract:

This study set out to identify the variables influencing consumer satisfaction with service quality. Quantitative and qualitative research methods are combined. After the famous service quality scholar's theoretical analysis, the elements influencing the customer satisfaction assessment model and the quality of service and satisfaction were examined. To put the model to the test, the study was undertaken. On a small scale, 300 questionnaires with 30 variables were gathered and processed for a qualitative study. Results All of the variables that were observed were found to be adequate by Cronbach's Alpha analysis. Next, multivariate statistical analysis is used in quantitative research methodologies, including Cronbach's alpha testing, factor analysis, correlation analysis, regression, and analysis of variance. From 300 valid questionnaires from customer research results show that there are six factors in the model study has implications for the level of impact are arranged in the following order: (1) the reliability, (2) tangible factors, (3) convenience, (4) sympathy, (5) guarantees, (6) the price. Finally the results of the study also indicate the contribution and significance, limitations and directions study for future research.

Keywords: business, satisfaction, spss, economy

1. Introduction

For many years, services have played a major role and have always accounted for a large share of our country's economic structure. Tourism service is seen as an important economic sector with the potential for fast expansion, greatly contributing to the country's total economic development in the next years. Apart from the efforts of the government, it is vital to emphasize the substantial contributions of travel firms and commercial enterprises in order to preserve the tourist industry's growing momentum. Because hotel services are an essential component of the tourist industry. So how to attract more and more tourists to Vietnam and how to "retain" tourists, make visitors feel completely satisfied and have a good impression of a Vietnam is something that not only the Vietnam National Administration of Tourism and the tourism industry must think about, but also business enterprises try to satisfy their customers.

2. Literature review

Markovic and Respor (2010) conducted research on assessing hotel service quality by perception using the SERVQUAL scale. According to the findings of the study, four criteria influence the quality of hotel services: reliability, empathy, staff competency, capacity to meet (accessibility), and tangible features (Tangibles). Rodolfo Vázquez (2001) Investigate the characteristics that influence service quality in supermarkets. The study's goal is to explain and extend the ideas and assessment of service quality in the retail sector. After reviewing the literature on retail and service quality, as well as qualitative and quantitative studies, the results show that for retail companies in the form of supermarkets, service quality is primarily influenced by four major factors: physical

aspects, reliability, personal interaction, and policy. Satisfaction is a form of satisfaction after expectations and requirements have been met, they are formed through the process of experience and accumulation.

According to Kotler (2000), satisfaction is a feeling of satisfaction or disappointment of a person while Hansemark and Albinsson (2004) mentioned that satisfaction is a customer's attitude towards a service provider or an emotional response. In summary, research models on factors affecting customer satisfaction are listed with many factors. Aditya. K (2019) concluded that meeting the aspects of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty is the ultimate goal to be achieved for every organization, both in the manufacturing and service sectors. service. These are also fundamental elements for model building. Kotler and Armstrong (2004) define services as activities or benefits that businesses can contribute to customers to establish, maintain and expand long-term cooperation and relationships with customers. Or as Lovelock (2001) Oliveira (2009), service is an economic activity that creates value and provides benefits to customers at a specific time and place as a result of a desired change. wants, or on behalf of the recipient (using) the service. The Vietnamese standard system defines "Service is the result created by contact activities between suppliers to meet customer needs". Parasuraman et al (1985) proposed 10 aspects of service quality including: (1) reliability; (2) responsiveness; (3) service capacity; (4) access; (5) politeness (courtesy); (6) information (communication); (7) credibility (credibility); (8) security; (9) understanding customer; (10) tangible means. Subsequent studies have reduced these 10 aspects to 5 factors. Bitner et al (1993, citing Wolak et al, 1998) summarizes the main notions of service marketing researchers since the 1980s that services have four main characteristics: (1) intangibility, (2) inseparability, (3) heterogeneity, and (4) non-storability.

3. Research Methodology

To amend and enhance observable variables used to gauge study concepts, qualitative research employs conversation approaches with expert groups and customers. Following a hand-to-hand interview, scale components were developed based on the thoughts and ideas gathered. The draft scale is then adjusted through a group discussion. Following group discussion, construct a tentative scale. The preliminary scale findings comprise 30 observed variables and seven concepts employed in this study: (1) Reliability, (2) Response, (3) Assurance, (4) Tangibles, (5) Empathy, (6) Price, and (7) Satisfaction. The scale's intelligibility is then evaluated again before starting official study. Quantitative research is conducted by conducting direct interviews with customers using thorough questionnaires to evaluate scales and test theoretical models and assumptions.

The quantitative study was conducted in a 5-star hotel in the Ho Chi Minh City region. With the approach of gathering information by interviewing through questionnaires, the number of questionnaires issued was 350 pounds, and 310 pounds were collected and 300 pounds were included in the study from consumers who replied correctly. Quantitative research enables for the examination and assessment of elements influencing customer happiness and service excellence. The research was conducted in two stages:

Step 1: Conduct a few customer interviews. A draft questionnaire will be utilized in this phase, and a few clients will be interviewed. After gathering information from these clients, the research will identify any flaws, subjectivity in the questionnaire, or question overlaps. The questionnaire will then be adjusted in accordance with the findings of the study.

Step 2: Collect official data by distributing customer interview surveys with completed questionnaires.

4. Research result and discussion

Table 1: The general information of the respondents

Demographic		Quantity	(%)
Sex	Male	167	55,6
	Female	133	44,3
Age	From 18 to 27 years old	183	61
	From 28 to 44 years old	72	24
	From 45 to 60 years old	36	12
	Above 60 years old	6	2
Academic level	University degrees	126	42
	Postgraduate	99	33
	High school	42	14
	Professional secondary	24	8
Job	Office workers	123	41
	Self-employed	60	20
	Business	51	17
	Students	9	3
		300	100

In terms of gender, male consumers account for 55.6 percent of the overall sample, while female customers account for 133 persons, or 44.3% of the total sample. The age group 18 to 27 accounts for 61 percent, followed by the age group 28 to 44 years old at 24 percent, the age group 45 - 60 years old at 12 percent, the age group > 60 years old at 2 percent, and the remaining 1 percent age 18 years old. Customers with university degrees account for 42 percent; customers with college degrees account for 33 percent; customers with postgraduate qualifications account for 14 percent; customers with high school education account for 8 percent; and customers with professional secondary education account for at least 3 percent. According to the findings of this poll, office employees account for 41 percent of clients; self-employed people account for 20 percent; business customers account for 17 percent, and students account at just 3 percent.

Table 2: Cronbach's Alpha reliability test results and KMO

Factor	Number of variables observe	Cronbach's Alpha	Coefficient minimum total variable correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if the variable type is smallest value	Conclusion
Reliability	4	0.832	0.687	0.808	Qualified
Assurance	4	0.820	0.864	0.912	Qualified
Response	4	0.811	0.651	0.771	Qualified
Tangibles	4	0.945	0.792	0.856	Qualified
Empathy	4	0.783	0.756	0.819	Qualified
Price	4	0.902	0.951	0.967	Qualified
Satisfaction	4	0.702	0.691	0.868	Qualified

According to the data table above, the factors appear to have a very high level of confidence because the majority of the coefficients of all the independent and dependent variables are greater than 0.7, and the correlation between variables and the total variable (Corrected item-total Correlation) is greater than 0.3, indicating that the scale is greater than 0.3. The aforementioned measurements are reasonable, realistic, and statistically significant. Variables having Cronbach's Alpha coefficients that are less than the group's Cronbach's Alpha coefficient (save in one specific circumstance) should be preserved for component analysis.

Table 3: Factor loading of independent variables

Rotated Component Matrixa						
	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
RB1	0,652					
RB2	0,683					
RB3	0,674					
RB4	0,531					
AS1		0,941				
AS2		0,936				
AS3		0,858				
AS4		0,788				
RP1			0,842			
RP2			0,751			
RP3			0,787			
RP4			0,631			
TB1				0,732		
TB2				0,710		
TB3				0,633		
TB4				0,622		
EP1					0,867	
EP2					0,680	
EP3					0,696	

EP4					0,659	
PR1						0,718
PR2						0,623
PR3						0,644
PR4						0.743

The factor rotation matrix table demonstrates that the observed variables' factor loading coefficients all have values greater than 0.6. Based on the results of the preceding investigation, the scale has good reliability and is utilized in regression analysis to assess the influence of independent factors on satisfaction. As a result, the scale of factors influencing the retrieved components is both trustworthy and valid. The scales meet the requirements for confirmatory factor analysis.

Table 4: Synthesis analysis ANOVA

Model	Sumof Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	35,031	6	5,688	101,342	0,000
Residual	17,286	293	0,056		
Total	51,417	299			

The sig values are all very small (sig.=0.00) showing that the variables are statistically significant.

5. Recommendation

This factor has the lowest positive influence on customer satisfaction with hotel service quality, so it should be promoted to increase the price satisfaction level of the hotel. hotels with several solutions as follows: The hotel strengthens promotions during the tourist season in the last months of the year to increase competitiveness with rivals. Regularly monitor information about the demand of the tourism industry and forecasts from the Vietnam National Administration of Tourism to adjust prices to suit the market. Hotel management must remind employees to save input costs to maintain competitive prices compared to competitors.

The level of influence on satisfaction is not high, so to increase the hotel's assurance ability, hotel managers and staff need: It is necessary to remind employees to always keep a polite and friendly attitude towards customers. Pay attention to regular training on hotel operations for staff to have a professional working style. Especially foreign language training for all employees to improve understanding of customers. To ensure absolute safety for customers and guests' property, the luggage locker management area must have a surveillance camera to avoid confusion or theft. The problem of preventing fire and explosion, and electric shock must always be carefully aware by all hotel staff. Because the bedrooms are located next to each other, it is very dangerous if not careful. The empathy factor is rated by customers with the highest points. This factor has a positive influence on customer satisfaction with hotel service quality, The research gives some suggestions such as all hotel managers and staff must understand their mission is to serve customers to have a caring attitude to understand each

guest's needs. Beautifully displayed in the hotel lobby, there are fresh flowers every day at the waiting table at the hotel reception hall. Cleanliness must be the top priority in the bedroom, and in the bathroom. Invest in upgrading more advanced equipment in the bedroom. Checking and fully equipping headphones to serve the needs of guests listening to music and watching television. Staff always wear well-groomed and beautiful clothes to make customers feel that they are warmly welcomed. The hotel must pay attention to improving the transaction of providing information and receiving bookings for customers via email quickly and accurately. The actual check-in must match the commitments made by the pictures provided to customers to see on the hotel's website.

6. Conclusion

This study uses the service quality scale SERVPERF of Cronin and Taylor (1992), the price scale of Mayhew and Winer (1992), and the customer satisfaction scale of Oliver (1997) to evaluate the service quality. Factors affecting customer satisfaction with hotel service quality. Thereby, we need discovering, adjusting, and supplementing the scales, verifying the conclusions of previous researchers on service quality scales for the hotel sector. The analysis results in the above chapters show that the research objectives of the topic have been solved: Determine the factors and the extent of their impact on customer satisfaction. Research has shown that price is the most urgent factor that hotel managers need to find solutions to increase customer satisfaction. Suggest some managerial implications to improve customer satisfaction in the near future.

Conflict of interests

None

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